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CORRELATION OF SPEECH AND GLOBAL STRATEGIES IN POLITICAL DISCOURSE AND DISCOURSE OF INTERNET COMMUNICATION

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Abstract

Contemporary linguistics contains numerous studies dedicated to researching political discourse against the background of any military actions. The present research is dedicated to studying the implementation of the CONFRONTATION strategy in the discourse of Internet communication as a consequent responsive reaction to the strategies realised in the political discourse against the background of the ongoing military actions in Ukraine and published in different social media. This work aims to show the direct correlation between the initial nature of political content, published or reported on the matter of the military actions in Ukraine in the media and the responsive nature of the feedback to it provided in posts or comments to this content. English and German spoken and/or written public statements by high-ranking officials, deputies and political leaders, dedicated to the daily events and changes in Ukraine as well as comments related to them, posted on social media will be used as research material. The scientific novelty of this study lies in the following: the classification of psychological strategies of self-presentation is for the first time used in the context of speech strategies realised in political discourse to implement global strategies, in particular – influencing the target audience; the strategy of emotional propaganda for the first time acquires the definition of a global strategy of political discourse.

Keywords: political discourse, media discourse, Internet communication, communicative strategy, global strategy, manipulation, persuasion, propaganda, confrontation, causality, causal relations.

Since ancient times the phenomenon of political discourse has attracted the attention of philosophers and representatives of other humanities. Being a multi-disciplinary phenomenon, political discourse has been not only the focus of linguistics but also of social studies.

Within the framework of the present research, we find it completely appropriate to identify the notion of political discourse with the one of political rhetoric.

The first attempts to single out political rhetoric as an independent type of speech activity go back to ancient times: it is from there that rhetoric originates – one of the three key ancient discursive directions, which was located next to grammar and logic/dialectic, and one of the main tasks of which is, first, the strategy of PERSUASION. The very first mentions of rhetoric date back to the 5th century, BC. (10, p. 1; 15)

In the light of philosophical studies, rhetoric is highlighted within the teachings of the sophist philosophers, who defined it not only as a set of means of argumentation and, accordingly, persuasion but as a key educational discipline – rhetoric studies, which delves into the study of persuasive language, examining how rhetoric constructs political realities and impacts communication. (15; 36)

Aristotle, in turn, had a somewhat different and deeper view of rhetoric, not considering it an art of creation, instead giving it the definition of an art of action, namely, the embodiment of power realised through speech: the philosopher was the first to speak of humans as of “political animals” due to their ability to express their thoughts verbally. (2; 3; 15)

A big significance to the phenomenon of political rhetoric was also given by Roman rhetoricians, such as

Cicero and Quintilian, who emphasised the political advantages of rhetoric, certainly referring to their Greek forerunners, including Gorgias, Plato, Isocrates, and Aristotle. (17, p. 38)

Since in many cases, the addressee on the influence of which both his speech and non-speech strategies are oriented in the political discourse is the society, the use of political-discursive practices is also widely covered in psychology.

Given the direct connection between political discourse and the discourse of power, we consider it reasonable within the framework of this study to establish a correlation between the exercise of power and the individual’s need for it. Thus, there is a need to provide a classification of individual needs, the brightest and most illustrative of which in the field of modern psychological research is the so-called “pyramid”, modelled and presented in 1943 by the American psychologist A. Maslow, which graphically represents the hierarchy of human needs. This is, in particular, a classification of human needs, which is based on human goal setting, and according to which “human needs are located in a hierarchy” (41, p. 370). They include *physiological needs, the safety need, the need for self-esteem, the need for love* and finally *the need for self-actualization*, which is the last and the highest stage in the hierarchy of human needs. (41, pp. 394-395)

While the first stages of Maslow’s hierarchy embrace primarily basic and instinctive needs, the need for power can rather be related to both esteem and self-actualization, which belong to the highest stages of the pyramid and are not the needs possessed by every individual. *The esteem need* is here realized through the desire for power and often aligns with the need for recognition and respect from others, while *the need for self-*

actualization in this context is manifested in achieving positions of influence or making a significant impact that can fulfil this need properly.

The study of political rhetoric within social psychology unveils the art of persuasion, the complexities of language, and their impact on democratic processes. In the realm of social psychology, interest in rhetoric has grown as part of the “*turn to language*” movement. This movement rejects cognitivism and emphasises approaching talk and text as strategic communicative actions rather than mere expressions of inner psychological processes.

It is worth mentioning that the tendency to consider rhetoric as the art of communication has survived to nowadays: representatives of contemporary digital humanities, e. G. E. Losh, in her development of J. Habermas’s theories, postulates that digital technology and electronic networks enable public rhetoric, especially from political institutions, to reach a wider audience. G. E. Losh shows how classical rhetorical principles, such as the right timing and the types of rhetoric that Aristotle identified, can help us understand and evaluate digital texts. She also explores how digital rhetoric can create new forms and modes of expression that challenge or change the conventional ones. She argues that digital rhetoric is not only about how to communicate effectively but also about the ethical and political implications of doing so. (35, pp. 47-48)

In the meantime, within some other scientific research digital rhetoric is argued to be not only a matter of style or technique but also a matter of ethics and politics as it involves questions of power, identity, and participation in the public sphere. (59; 63)

S. Condor, along with her colleagues, has contributed significantly to the study of political rhetoric. Their work sheds light on the strategies used to construct persuasive arguments in political debates. (9)

The topic of political rhetoric spans various academic disciplines and touches upon the fundamental activities of democratic politics: the role of ambivalence and vagueness in democratic political life is revealed as identities are claimed, displayed, and attributed during political discourse. (28)

The direct focus of our research is political discourse (in the context of our work identified with political rhetoric), namely, political public address as a discursive phenomenon that has a strategic nature. Thus, the existing experience of studying the phenomenon of political discourse in the field of linguistic studies is of key importance for this research.

The fundamental works performed in the realm of discourse analysis offer deep insights into political discourse and mechanisms that shape it and therefore can be considered a valuable contribution both to discourse analysis and political science. Thus, it is reasonable and appropriate to provide a short overview of the political discourse definitions and descriptions, given in some of the main and widely known linguistic research papers.

T. A. van Dijk, the “founding father” of discourse analysis, in one of his works defines political discourse as a compilation of all discursive activity, which is both “the text and talk” realised by the political actors, such as presidents, heads and/or members of governments,

leaders, members and/or speakers of different political organisations, both at the internal and external levels. (11, p. 12)

Unlike some other fields of discursive practices (medical, legal, or educational discourse), the political discourse can be characterized by the vast number of participants, who bring this discourse to action. The politicians here are “actors”, who are often the ones to produce the initial messages, while the audience, to which these messages are directed, are the “recipients”. (11, p. 13) The latter in turn might also be conditionally divided into various groups by the criterion of what kind of function they have in terms of political discourse (voters, citizens, rebellions etc.). (56)

R. Wodak is another renowned linguist who has intensively engaged with the notion of political discourse. A range of her investigations conducted in the field of pragmatic linguistics are devoted to considering the various manifestations of political discourse phenomena from different perspectives.

The work “Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA)” (2003) performs the quintessence of reflection and construction of power ideologies and relations in discourse and enables the profound understanding of the language importance in creating the social realities by the individuals. (60)

In the book “The Discourse of Politics in Action: Politics as Usual” the researcher investigates how politicians “do politics” on a micro level and how they operate in everyday life within the halls of the European Parliament. In essence, the definition of political discourse, presented by R. Wodak, comprises not just the language used in politics, but also the social practices, power dynamics and the professional habits of politicians. (61)

“The Politics of Fear. The Shameless Normalization of Far-right Discourse”, published in 2021, provides an interpretation of some political discursive practices, such as “coded language”, that started to be used by the politicians to “sound” more restraint in the light of the 20th century’s almost overall totalitarianism results. (62, p. 68)

J. Habermas, a German philosopher and social theorist, whose works are widely engaged with linguistic theories and concepts, developed a theory of language based on the concept of communicative rationality. The scientist was also the one to apply his linguistic theory to analyse various forms of communication such as law, democracy, and media, having written extensively on political discourse.

According to J. Habermas, political discourse is a form of rational communication that aims to reach a consensus about the common good. Political discourse involves the use of valid arguments, evidence, and norms that can be justified in an ideal speech situation, where everyone has equal access and opportunity to participate. Political discourse is based on the principle of discourse ethics, which holds that only those norms and actions are valid and can be agreed upon by all affected parties in a rational dialogue.

Summarising the experience of defining and describing the phenomenon of political discourse performed in the works by J. Habermas related to this topic, the following set of goals has been achieved:

- ❖ Development of a discourse theory of democracy and law, based on the idea of an ideal speech situation where rational communication leads to a consensus about a common good; (24)
- ❖ Exploration of the concept of communicative rationality, which is the capacity to coordinate action through speech that implies validity claims; (22)
- ❖ Discussing the role of the media and the public sphere in contemporary society. (23)

The research of the early 21st century stick to the argument that language is in the centre of political activity, being the main condition of its realisation. (21, p. 1) This statement roots back to the pragmatic linguistic studies, namely – to the speech acts theory, which grants the language with the pragmatic features: “speaking means acting”. (1; 45)

Since the political discourse in the present research is considered against the background of mass media and social networks, it is appropriate to emphasize that both are important fields for political discourse, as they enable the production, dissemination, and exchange of political information and opinions among diverse actors and audiences. The media space has become a significant counterpart to traditional political discourse, political conversations, and advertisements. (42; 58)

Social networks and mass media can influence the public agenda, political participation and the political outcomes of elections and policies, and they have significantly transformed the field of political discourse: social media platforms like Twitter and Facebook are increasingly used in a political context. They are believed to have the potential for increasing political participation. (50)

In the context of mass media political discourse has undergone significant changes with the advent of new technologies and the rise of social media platforms (social networks). Some of these transformations are:

- ❖ **Mediatization of Politics.** Political discourse is increasingly mediatized meaning that media has become an integral part of political communication. (8)
- ❖ **Marketization of Media.** The field of Media has become marketized, which means that market forces and commercial interests drive it. (8)
- ❖ **Framing and Agenda Setting.** The media has the power to frame political issues and set the public agenda. (19)

However, they also pose challenges and risks to the quality and integrity of political discourse, such as:

The spread of misinformation and fake news on social media platforms is a significant risk to the political discourse quality and integrity, as it provides false information, thereby misleading the audience which can be referred to MANIPULATION strategy.

Social media platforms can also create spaces, called “*echo chambers and filter bubbles*”, where individuals are exposed primarily to opinions that align with their own. This, in turn, can lead to **polarisation**

in discourse: the phenomenon, where language or actions attract or reinforce an individual’s position on a binary or what they view as a binary. (4; 6; 19)

The notion of **censorship** within the mass media and social networks refers to the practice of suppressing and restricting content that is considered objectionable, harmful, sensitive, or inconvenient by governments, media outlets or other controlling bodies. (27; 48; 49; 54; 55)

On the positive side, social networks and mass media have democratised access to information, allowing more people to participate in political discourse. (57)

These aspects highlight the complexity of political discourse in the era of mass media and social networks and the need for media literacy among the public. (47)

In terms of this research, political discourse is considered as such, that is not only realised in terms of mass media and social networks but is also interconnected with the discourse of the media space, or media discourse. Moreover, the way the initial message is produced in the realm of political discourse might significantly differ from how it is transmitted in the media. (Wilson 1990: 17) Therefore, we find it reasonable and appropriate to pay special attention to outlining the latter as a linguistic phenomenon, as well as highlighting its interdisciplinary connections.

A significant contribution to the further development of media discourse as a direction of discursive studies was made by T. A. van Dijk, namely – his theory of social interaction, in terms of which the researcher defines discourse as one of its forms. Applying the socio-cognitive approach, the scientist concentrates on the cognitive aspects of discursive activity realisation and perception, which, in turn, enables the definition of media discourse as such, which is created via the cognitive processes of media users. (14; Mammadov 2022)

In his work “What is political discourse analysis?” Dijk sets a parallel between the phenomenon of political discourse, overviewed in the previous paragraph of this paper, and the notion of media discourse, which can also be characterised by a large number of participants, towards whom this activity is directed. (11, p. 13)

At the same time, T. A. van Dijk argues for the absence of a direct and immediate connection between discursive and social structures considering the discourse functioning through the prism of cognitive connections instead. Such a point of view might be used for a more detailed interpretation and understanding of how social networks and mass media influence discourse and vice versa. (12)

The research by T. A. van Dijk, performed on the surface of critical discourse analysis, studies the discursive implementation of social power, and, consequently – inequity. This perspective can serve as a starting point in considering discursive reproduction, in other words – verbalization of power in terms of media space. (13)

Investigations of the linguist, realised directly in the media discourse area evidence the fact of constructing the social reality by the media texts, which, in turn, provides an opportunity for in-depth studying the social networks discourse. It is beyond any doubts, that the occasion, a political speech or statement is devoted to,

as well as its target audience are not only immediately correlated, but also significantly influence the substantial core, selection by the speaker of the engaged strategies, as well as variousity of their implementation. (11; 12; 13; 61)

R. Wodak is inclined to consider media discourse as such that, due to its daily enormous production, has a capacity of producing a big influence on the audience, especially in Western society: “people watch or read ‘news’ because they think ‘news’ is about reality”. (60, p. 274) Media makers, including broadcasting, publishing institutions and nowadays – those who produce content on the platforms of social networks, in attempting to “establish and protect democracy” demonstrate a significant extent of autonomy and freedom, sometimes – even despite the conditions of imposing censorship. (60, p. 298)

M. Talbot in “Media Discourse: Representation and Interaction” defines media discourse as such, that has a function of mediation, and namely in terms of the present research – a mediation platform between the actors of political discourse and their target audience, the function of which belongs to the population. (53)

Therefore, it is considered to be a wide interaction field that provides a “solid ground” to emphasise the interdisciplinary connections of media discourse with linguistic anthropology, sociolinguistics and cultural studies.

The area of media discourse as a linguistic phenomenon has also become one of the nowadays linguistic researchers’ foci, particularly – in discourse studies, especially regarding the rapid development of digitalization. It involves the analysis of language and discourse in various social media contexts as well as the study of language changes induced by social media and the relationship between language variation and society in the digital world. (34; 52)

The up-to-date linguistic research works on the discourse of mass media and social networks provide an extensive overview of the current state of investigation in the field of media discourse in the linguistics realm. They highlight the importance of considering the social and cognitive aspects of discourse, which are crucial for understanding communication on the media platforms; discuss the impact of social media content on the way people interact and share information, as well as the role of media linguistics in the language of modern mass media; prove that most social media texts are short online conversational posts or comments that do not contain enough information for natural language processing (NLP) tools; present the “status quo” of linguistic studies on social media in the past decade and define seven main research methods. (5; 32; 52)

Some researchers criticise the linear “top-down” model of media-space, which is depicted as “sender-receiver”, arguing that the imposing of the produced content, and accordingly – its meaning on the audience often takes place. (25)

Texts presented in the media space, in particular – placed on social network platforms, in most cases, take the form of posts or comments on them and are often immersed in a non-linguistic contextual environment,

which can be served by the user’s profile and his interaction with other users of the social network. Thus, taking into account the social-communicative interaction, the discourse of mass media and social networks can be characterised as more difficult to process than ordinary texts published in real-time, because social media posts often lack a clear structure and format, as they belong to different users, and correspondingly – composed in different languages and have stylistic differences. (5)

These studies underscore the significant impact of mass media and social networks on language and discourse, making it a rich area for linguistic research, and offering insights into how language is used in these digital platforms. The investigations also provide evidence that media discourse has a major role in such key fields of linguistics as pragmatics and Critical Discourse Analysis.

Besides being a linguistic phenomenon, the discourse of media is widely investigated in humanities, revealing its strong interdisciplinary connections.

In the last decades, we have witnessed a sustainable and rapid development of digitalization, the access to the Internet became available in no effort, and the consumption indicators of the content produced and published on mass media platforms and social networks are getting higher. A wide range of studies conducted in the fields of psychology, sociology and social psychology is devoted to revealing the statistical data, which would demonstrate the indicators of addressing to various sources of information on mass and social media as well as the degree of their influence on consciousness, mentality, and mental state of the users, without mentioning the constantly developing software, that is engaged in gathering the data showing how frequent various online-sources are used or even just visited.

A field of Internet communication, in particular – the discursive activity in social networks might be considered as a wide branch of media discourse and thus represents a big area of linguistic research. Some of its aspects are already lightened, nevertheless there are still a lot of perspectives to see.

Military actions taking place in Ukraine created a huge field not only for political, but also for linguistic research. The discourse of wartime brings its significant changes to the social communication process, moreover nowadays, when Internet-access is no longer a problem.

The hypothesis of the present research lies in the supposition that there is a direct correlation between the speech and global strategies implemented in the political discourse and the strategy of CONFRONTATION as a responsive reaction, realised in the discourse of Internet communication, as feedback to the political statements: the local strategies, realised by the politicians serve a trigger, provoking implementation of CONFRONTATION towards them by the users of social networks as ones who impersonate the so-called “people’s voice”.

Within the framework of the present article the local strategies rendered by the politicians in their statements, posted on social-media platforms, namely – on

the platform X (former Twitter) were categorized according to the taxonomy of self-presentation strategies, generated by E. Jones and T. S. Pittman. (30, pp. 231-262)

INGRATIATION strategy is aimed at causing the favour of the addressee with an attempt of the speaker to appear attractive in the eyes of the addressee. This strategy involves the “*power of charm*”. (30, p. 235)

SELF-PROMOTION strategy is somewhat similar to INGRATIATION, but is directed at demonstrating one's own competence in certain issues. SELF-PROMOTION correlates with the technique of “showing-off” and involves the “*power of expert*”. (30, p. 241)

INTIMIDATION strategy correlates with the “*power of fear*” and corresponds the technique of making demands and/or threatening. The speaker has to impose the addressee their being dangerous in case, when the latter refuses to do what they are required to. (30, p. 238)

One more strategy is EXEMPLIFICATION, which means explanation through example. This strategy involves manifesting one's skills and engaging the “*power of mentor*”. Here the task of the speaker is to convince the addressee, that the former can be the one to follow and listen to. (30, p. 245)

The last strategy is SUPPLICATION, demonstration of weakness and dependence; it aims at appearing before the addressee as a weak, dependent person, whose esteem is not very high. This strategy engages the “*power of sympathy*” and correlates with the tactic of *self-handicapping*. (30, p. 247)

The classification of speech strategies developed in the previous research (31) defines three types of speech strategies, namely – *metaspeech* (with the aim of contact establishment), strategy of *informing* (aimed to deliver any kind of message to the addressee) and strategy of *assessment* (with the purpose of positive or negative evaluation of self, the addressee or different phenomena). Within this study the strategies stated above were generated to describe verbalizing of self-presentation. Hereby we find it appropriate to apply them in analysis of the comments to the political statements.

Choosing different classifications for conducting the strategic analysis of political statements and comments to them can be explained by the higher level of implementation of self-presentation strategies as local ones by the politicians, whose aim is to produce the desired impression on their voters, whereby the commentators are usually average citizens who exercise the freedom of speech to express their opinion.

A basis for classifying and identifying global strategies used in political discourse, as well as varieties of the global strategy of CONFRONTATION in the discourse of Internet communications, was the list of GLOBAL STRATEGIES presented in a previously conducted dissertation research.

The empiric material, gathered for this article, manifested that the political discourse engages the global strategies of COOPERATIVE APPROACHING, MANIPULATION, PERSUASION and the strategy of EMOTIONAL PROPAGANDA.

The global strategy of COOPERATIVE APPROACHING is, as defined in the previous research, aimed at reducing the communicative distance between speaker and addressee or initiation of interaction between them. Besides, in both cases, the synergistic nature of these strategies should be taken into account, in particular, adding to these definitions that increasing/decreasing communicative distance can be cooperative – such that contributes to harmonization of interpersonal relationships, or at least does not threaten them. (31, p. 156)

MANIPULATION, in terms of this paper, is regarded as a strategy that refers to the use of mass media and social networks to influence public opinion or behaviour in a way that serves the interests of a certain group, often through deceptive and or unethical means. In the realm of linguistic research, the strategy of MANIPULATION is considered as a mechanism for achieving the goal of the initiator of communication, who seeks to embed certain information in the consciousness of the addressee, which can mean an attempt to correct his worldview and value system. (18; 31, p. 180; 43)

PERSUASION strategy comes from the notion of persuasiveness. The latter in turn is defined as the influence of the author of an oral or written message upon the addressee with the aim of persuading him, encouraging him to perform/not perform certain actions. A persuasive strategy is also considered multi-level structure, which, in turn, actualizes the interaction of argumentative actions / steps in order to substantiate the central conclusion. (7, p. 24; 26, p. 78)

The next to describe will be the strategies of RATIONAL and EMOTIONAL ARGUMENTATION, which actually belong to the PERSUASIVE strategy.

RATIONAL ARGUMENTATION is correlated with rational thinking, and/or with the “common sense”, the aim of which is considered to be substantiation and widening of the knowledge authenticity of an array of logic as well as gnoseologic procedures. (Sergeev 1987: 12) The strategy of RATIONAL ARGUMENTATION might be interpreted as a complex socio-cognitive verbal activity aimed at justifying or refuting a certain point of view. (37, p. 6)

EMOTIONAL ARGUMENTATION is implemented by means of “semantically empty” emotive attributes or stylistic (stylistic-semasiological) techniques – tropes, which are reproduced using both lexical (figurative words or idioms), as well as syntactic units (if the trope has an expanded form and embodied in a phrase, a sentence or a larger text fragment). (29, pp. 4-5; 38, p. 50; 40, p. 243).

SUGGESTION is considered as a psychological influence on the consciousness of an individual with a purpose suggesting to him desired attitudes, which are not realized and contradict of his will (51) as “the process of influencing the mental sphere of the unconscious, connected with a decrease in criticality during the perception of implied content in the absence of purposeful active understanding of it, detailed logical analysis, and evaluations in correlation with the past experience and the current state of the subject” (44).

The named characteristics allow us to consider SUGGESTION as an influence which is qualitatively opposed to PERSUASION, where the action is on the consciousness of the individual occurs through an appeal to her own critical judgment (33).

One more global strategy, which appears and is considered in the realm of this research is EMOTIONAL PROPAGANDA. Generally, it is somewhat related to EMOTIONAL ARGUMENTATION but has a little different nature.

The phenomenon of *propaganda* is referred to an attempt to manipulate the beliefs of an addressee or to impose them a certain point of view or attitude, which would be advantageous for the implementors of propaganda. Usually, propagandists have a certain set of goals and in order to achieve them, facts and arguments, which are about to be publicly presented, experience a lot of changes. (16)

Within the framework of the present research the EMOTIONAL PROPAGANDA is regarded as a global strategy intended to produce an effect on the emotions of the addressee, which is realised in the dimension of MANIPULATION STRATEGY.

At first glance, the strategy of EMOTIONAL PROPAGANDA manifests no differences from that of EMOTIONAL ARGUMENTATION. The peculiarity

both of them have in common lies in the emotional impact they are intended to produce on the addressee. Nevertheless, there is also a very important feature that make them differ from one another, namely – the goal of realising each of them: while EMOTIONAL ARGUMENTATION is proven to aim at PERSUADING the opponent, EMOTIONAL PROPAGANDA is intended to realize MANIPULATION of the opponent's attitudes and beliefs. Thus, both these strategies engage emotional impact, but have different global goals.

The strategy of CONFRONTATION is described in a range of works as well and is based on the model "I am higher, you are lower". In our work we implement the experience of our previous research, where the CONFRONTATION strategy has two variants of realisation, namely – CONFRONTATIVE APPROACHING, which aims at conflict shortening of the distance between the communicants, and CONFRONTATIVE DISTANCING, which means opposition of the one communicant to the other. (20; 31)

The scheme given below renders the realization of global and speech strategies in the political discourse as well as the varieties of CONFRONTATION strategies in Internet communication and their correlation with the speech strategies, implemented in Internet-discourse.

Fig. 1. Interaction of political discourse communicative strategies and the strategy of CONFRONTATION in Internet communication.

The analysed empiric material reveals the implementation of the above-stated strategies as follows.

(1) Statement: *Total disregard for human life and constant terror is what Russia is trying to spread. <...> Protecting life in Ukraine with a sufficient number of air defence systems, providing our soldiers with the*

necessary weapons of the required range, and exerting pressure on the terrorist state so that Russia does not have time to adapt is the way to bring peace closer. Russian terror must lose. The world is capable of ensuring this. (83)

Comment: *You are the one destroying Ukraine, little dictator.* (73)

The example (1) contains the text of the post at the official profile of the Ukrainian President V. Zelensky on the platform X (former Twitter). The fragment manifests realisation of such strategies as INTIMIDATION (the word “terror” is used to provoke the fear of the addressee), and SUPPLICATION, verbalized through “*The world is capable of ensuring this*”, meaning that the world community is capable of sustainable supporting Ukraine. The abovementioned correlates with the global strategies of COOPERATIVE APPROACHING (V. Zelensky uses the word combination “*our soldiers*”, which is more colloquial, in an official statement, in order to position himself verbally closer to his nation) and EMOTIONAL PROPAGANDA (an attempt to influence the emotions of the audience by the means of repeating the word “terror” in order to produce fear and anxiety as well as strengthening adjective “total” in “*total disregard of human life*”) as well as in the statement “*Russian terror must lose*” the modal verb “*must*”, which means the highest degree of obligation, was used by the speaker rather as an emotional marker to emphasize the importance of the utterance.

A bright example illustrating engaging CONFRONTATION strategy in comments is a responding comment to the given political statement, which involves such speech strategies as **assessment**, and tactic of *negative assessment*: the author of the comment claims the Ukrainian President to be “*destroying Ukraine*”. Within the same strategy and tactic implementing irony and sarcasm can also be observed: the commentator calls V. Zelensky a “*little dictator*”, aiming at showing him cruel and ridiculous. Another important speech strategy, realized in the given fragment, is that of **informing**, involving the tactic of *asserting*, which is rendered in the purpose of the whole utterance. The global strategies implemented in this fragment are represented, first of all, by the strategy of CONFRONTATIONAL APPROACHING: the author of the comment addresses the President by the means of the personal pronoun “*you*” in the 2nd person singular, which in Ukrainian language, as well as in German, means shortening the distance between the conversation partners. Given the general connotation of the whole utterance, the aim of such distance shortening is confrontation.

(2) Statement: *Der wirtschaftliche Schaden für unser Land, der durch die mutmaßlich von #Selenskyj – und nicht etwa #Putin, wie man uns weismachen wollte – angeordnete Sprengung von #Nordstream entstanden ist, sollte der #Ukraine "in Rechnung" gestellt werden. Jegliche den deutschen Steuerzahler belastende "Hilfszahlungen" sind einzustellen.* (64)

Comment: *Es ist beeindruckend, wie vorsichtig Sie sich ausdrücken. Ich bin jedoch der Meinung, dass Sie im Unrecht sind. Ihre Worte lassen lediglich Ihre Nähe zu Putin erkennen. Die Vorstellung, dass Taucher von einer Segeljacht aus der Pipeline zerstört haben könnten, ist geradezu lächerlich – technisch schlichtweg unmöglich.* (78)

The given example represents the statement dedicated to the explosion at the Nordstream gas-pipeline,

published on the official account of Dr. Alice Weidel – a German politician from the party AfD (Alternative für Deutschland), where she expresses her opinion towards what happened.

Considering the local strategies, represented in this statement, the ones to be implemented here were INGRATIATION (affirming that “*Jegliche den deutschen Steuerzahler belastende "Hilfszahlungen" sind einzustellen*”, the politician shows her being concerned about the German working population, which corresponds to an attempt to be liked by the target audience) and INTIMIDATION: the statement contains the affirmation, that Ukraine will have to pay the dues for all of the support it received from Germany, which is certainly not a very nice perspective for the Ukrainian population from the financial point of view, besides the politician marks the word “Ukraine” with the hashtag, which facilitates finding this post on the X platform and correspondingly potentially broadens the number of users who can read it. The global strategies, implemented here, are COOPERATION (the utterance “*unser Land*” as well as the intonation of the whole statement demonstrate that the politician positions herself along with her people, trying to get closer to her electorate), and EMOTIONAL PROPAGANDA (expressing her resentment with the financial help, provided to Ukraine by Germany, the politician claims it to be a burden for German tax-payers, with the aim to realise the emotional influence on the audience), and CONFRONTATION which is here implemented through verbalizing the idea of invoicing Ukraine for all the financial support it received from Germany as well as for the accident on the gas-pipe, for which, according to her opinion, Ukraine is the one to blame.

Strategic analysis of the responses to the given statement in the comments to it evidenced implementation of **assessment** with the tactic of *negative assessment*, verbalized in sarcastic manner (*Es ist beeindruckend, wie vorsichtig Sie sich ausdrücken.*). Along with that, the commentator renders also the **informing** strategy, involving the tactic of *announcing*, which is realised in notifying the politician about clarity of her true intentions. The CONFRONTATION rendered in the comment refers to CONFRONTATIVE DISTANCING, aimed at mocking an addressee with the aim of enlarging the communicative distance.

(3) Statement: *What happens to Ukraine matters to all of Europe, all of NATO, and all of the world. We are united against Putin's war. We are united behind Ukraine. And we are united behind a vision of the world where free countries never fear aggression from a brutal tyrant next door.* (76)

Comment: *What you are doing in Ukraine is robbing the American taxpayers blind to cover up yours and Hunters crimes over there... Hush money.* (70)

The political statement, represented in the example (3) was made by the President of the USA J. Biden and published on the social media platform X (former Twitter). Analysed from the point of view of the speech strategies, here, as well as in the most of previous fragments, the strategy of INGRATIATION was realized: *What happens to Ukraine matters to all of Europe, all of NATO, and all of the world.* The American President

reminds the audience, that Ukraine will not fight alone, thus trying to verbally produce a positive impression upon the target audience, in other words – to ingratiate the addressee. The global strategy, implemented in this fragment, is obviously EMOTIONAL PROPAGANDA: J. Biden resorts to such as repetition (*We are united against Putin's war. We are united behind Ukraine. And we are united behind a vision of the world <...>*) as well as emotionally marked vocabulary (*a brutal tyrant*). Therefore, J. Biden does not intend to manipulate, but is still inclined to emotionally persuade the audience in the necessity to continue providing Ukraine with necessary support, though his statement does not contain any explicit arguments.

The reaction to this statement rendered in the comment to it also involves the *informing* speech strategy, the tactic of *asserting*. The comment implies, that the President of the USA J. Biden is trying to cover up the crimes of the American government towards their own nation, e.g. “money laundering”, meaning that the aim of the USA hereby is not to support Ukraine, but to rob the American tax-payers. The global strategy of CONFRONTATION, namely CONFRONTATIVE APPROACHING is here realised through the disrespectful manner of communication, which is meant to shorten the distance with the addressee with confrontative purpose.

Another statement, made by J. Biden and published on his official account on the platform X (former Twitter) expresses the US President's being surprised with people, judging him and laughing him out for the reason of confusing the names of Russian and Ukrainian Presidents instead of paying attention to his political opponent D. Trump calling the actions of Russian Federation “genius” and “wonderful”.

(4) Statement: *When that butcher Putin invaded Ukraine, Trump called it “genius” and “wonderful”. But people would rather talk about how I mix up names.* (72)

Comment: *You literally bribed the Ukrainian government to fire a prosecutor and your son was taking money on your behalf from Ukraine. You are corrupt to your core.* (74)

This example contains also implementation of the implied EXEMPLIFICATION strategy: by understatement of D. Trump and V. Putin, J. Biden aims at showing himself as an example to follow, implying “*I am not the one to initiate military actions in the other country and not the one to approve it*”. Both of speech strategies realised in this fragment can here be associated with the global strategy of SUGGESTION as a part of PERSUASION strategy (an intention to convey certain kind of emotions to the audience), and EMOTIONAL PROPAGANDA, which are here interrelated. Using the emotionally marked words in an official statement, politician has the goal of underestimating his opponents in the eyes of the audience.

The given comment to this statement involves, first of all, *informing* speech strategy with the tactic of *asserting*, verbalised in the affirmation, that American President was the one to “*bribe the Ukrainian government*”, at the same time realising the strategy of *assessment* with the tactic of *negative assessment*, as well.

The only global strategy that can be observed here is CONFRONTATION, realised in CONFRONTATIVE APPROACHING: the commentator verbally shortens the distance between himself and the politician, using the disrespectful form of communication combined with the accusations on bribery and corruption.

The example (5) contains a political statement, made by the Chancellor of Germany O. Scholz, published on his official account with one of the comments to it, given below.

(5) Statement: *Germany is and will remain the strongest supporter of Ukraine in Europe. We will support Ukraine for as long as it takes. It was good meeting you today in Frankfurt, @ZelenskyyUa!* (66)

Comment: *Es ist ein zynischer, teurer und vor allem mörderischer Stellvertreterkrieg, der gegen den Willen der Bevölkerung, und haushaltswidrig, finanziert wird. Es könnte längst Frieden sein. Was Sie tun, Herr Scholz, ist verachtenswert.* (68)

The fragment (6) represents the political statement of R. Metsola – the current President of European Parliament, towards the events in Ukraine, published on her official account on the platform X (former Twitter) with one of the comments to it, written by one of the platform users.

(6) Statement: *Unwavering support, resolute assistance and firm commitment. We stand with Ukraine. Today, @Europarl_EN calls for further aid to Ukraine and for stronger sanctions against the aggressor and accomplices. To ensure Ukraine's sovereignty, security in Europe and peace.* (69)

Comment: *Roberta, you are failing the people of the EU by making them poorer. If you're failing us, why should the people of Ukraine have confidence in you? I believe you are a failure, and you'll fail them too. Will you resign if that happens?* (79)

In both of the statements, politicians appealed to the local strategies of INGRATIATION, directed at producing a positive impression upon the addressee, as well as implied EXEMPLIFICATION by positioning themselves as compassionate political leaders, whose example might be followed. Regarded through the prism of global strategies implementation, both fragments involve the strategy of COOPERATIVE APPROACHING, verbalized in intention to keep supporting Ukraine under any circumstances. SUGGESTION as a manifestation of PERSUASION, verbally implemented in, for example, using the superlative degree of comparison “*the strongest supporter*”, “*unwavering support*”, “*resolute assistance*” which intensifies the emotional influence of the utterance and aims at persuading the audience in the continuity of the further support, but at the same time contains no argumentation and therefore can be also considered as EMOTIONAL PROPAGANDA.

The speech strategies detected in the comment to the statement in fragment (5) belong, first of all, to *assessment* with the tactic of *negative assessment*. The commentator evaluates the actions of German Chancellor as something outrageous, using the utterances with the negative connotation (*zynisch, teuer, mörderisch*). Strategy of *informing* with the tactic of *asserting* is here realised in the utterance “*Es könnte längst Frieden*

sein”, where the speaker aims at pointing to the necessity of establishing peace. CONFRONTATION, namely CONFRONTATIONAL DISTANCING here can be observed in blaming O. Scholz for not fostering peace, and finds its implementation in this fragment in the utterance “Was Sie tun, Herr Scholz, ist verachtenswert”.

The strategic intentions of the comment to the statement of R. Metsola, given in the example (6), are similar to that of the fragment (5). First of all, the strategy of *assessment* with the tactic of *negative assessment* is here also implemented by the means of the word “fail” with a negative connotation, addressed to a politician. The strategy of *informing* with the tactic of *requesting information* is also realised here by the question “Will you resign if that happens?”, asking R. Metsola for resignation in case she “fails”. The strategy of CONFRONTATION, similarly to some of the previous fragments, is rendered in this fragment by CONFRONTATIONAL APPROACHING, namely – in shortening the communicational distance with the conflict purposes, expressed by the means of appealing to the politician in the comment using just her first name “Roberta”.

(7) Statement: *Great to be in Oslo for my last official visit and to meet my friend and colleague PM @jonasgahrstore. I welcomed #Norway's increased defence spending, reaching 2% of GDP, and its key support to #Ukraine. We addressed the importance of stepping up #NATO support so Ukraine can prevail.* (71)

Comment: *The farce rolls on, where the mass media's most important task is to lull the public into believing that Ukraine can win the war if we continue to uncontrollably deliver weapons and money on an assembly line so that the war industry remains satisfied and, above all, pushes for an escalation instead of peace negotiations.* (77)

This statement belongs to J. Stoltenberg – the General Secretary of the NATO Alliance, dedicated to one of his last official visits to Norway. Here the local strategy of INGRATIATION was implied in the whole utterance, namely in its attempt to appeal to the favour of the audience, positioning himself as an empathic politician. To the global strategies, realised in this statement belong, first of all, COOPERATIVE APPROACHING, which can be observed in the intention of the whole statement to foster collaboration with Ukraine and PERSUASION with the elements of RATIONAL ARGUMENTATION, revealed in providing a statistical report of “reaching the 2% of GDP”.

The speech strategies detected in the comment to this statement include, first of all, the strategy of *informing* with the tactic of *asserting* verbalized through the supposition of and mass media's attempt to fool the audience (“mass media's most important task is to lull the public”), as well as the strategy of *assessment* with the tactic of *negative assessment*, verbalized in “The farce rolls on” as well as in the negative evaluation of actions of international organisations towards what is going on in Ukraine: “pushes for an escalation instead of peace negotiations”. The strategy of

CONFRONTATION is here rendered in CONFRONTATIONAL DISTANCING and objectivates in the critics, expressed in the comment towards the politician.

(8) *Today's powerful discussions show the unique value of this #EuropeanPoliticalCommunity. Our resolve to support Ukraine is stronger than ever – we clearly reaffirmed that with President @ZelenskyyUa. Together we will ensure our energy security and take a comprehensive approach to the challenge of migration. Alone, these are daunting challenges.* (67)

Comment: *Don't you think that you go too far? Not a day goes by without hearing, reading #Ukraine or worse seeing #Zelensky. Simply, it's the best way to disgust a person than to serve them all the same dish even if it's their favourite...* (80)

Charles Michel, the President of the European Council, in his statement, similarly to his political colleagues in the previous statements engages the local strategy of INGRATIATION, by showing that as the head of one of the key European international organisations is actively participating in resolution of military conflicts: “resolve to support Ukraine is stronger than ever”. The global strategy, actualized in this fragment, is COOPERATIVE APPROACHING (“Together we will ensure our energy security and take a comprehensive approach <...>”, “Together, we will get it done”), aimed at expressing support and solidarity to the addressee.

The comment to this statement realises, first of all, the speech strategy of *informing* with the tactic of *requesting information* (using a rhetoric question “Don't you think that you go too far?” the commentator is inclined to point to the politician's being wrong) along with the strategy of *assessment*, with the tactic of *negative assessment* expressed in reprimanding him for excessively frequent mentioning Ukraine and its President V. Zelensky in his rhetoric. The global strategy of CONFRONTATION in its manifestation in CONFRONTATIVE DISTANCING is here rendered both with the above-mentioned rhetoric question, as well as with the intonation of the comment as a whole.

The fragments (9) and (10) belong to Ursula von der Leihen, the President of the EU Commission.

(9) Statement: *President @ZelenskyyUA, we will continue supporting Ukraine.* (81)

Comment: *It is unlikely that you have tried to negotiate peace. Then your meeting doesn't make sense.* (75)

(10) *Europe is the number one public investor in Ukraine's defence sector. Our EU Defence Innovation Office is up and running, with EU staff in Kyiv and a support team in Brussels. It works as a hub to connect Ukrainian and EU defence industries, to the benefit of both.* (82)

Comment: *No, Ursula. No. Europe do not have money. The money “Europe” waste is tax-payers money. People money. Workers' money. Is it clear? Or shall I explain it to that rotten thing you call brain and soul? Because trust me. You will meet a Judge. Soon. Why soon? Check your birth date.* (65)

Both statements realise the local strategy of INGRATIATION, which is here involved, like in the previous cases, to impress the audience positively: as the President of the EU Commission, U. von der Leihen identifies Europe as the main supporter and investor for Ukraine. The global strategy, that is realised in both fragments is COOPERATIVE APPROACHING, which is manifested in utterances like “<...> we will continue supporting Ukraine”, implying that the speaker, as the Head of key EU Organisations, identify themselves the same as the other EU Commission employees, ready to fulfil faithfully their obligations, and PERSUASION, implemented here with RATIONAL ARGUMENTATION, especially in example (10), where the politician provides arguments to the initial utterance: “Our EU Defence Innovation Office is up and running, with EU staff in Kyiv and a support team in Brussels. It works as a hub to connect Ukrainian and EU defence industries, to the benefit of both”.

As to the comments to these statements, they both realise the *informing* speech strategy with the tactic of *asserting* which in fragment (9) might be seen in the whole text of the comment and in fragment (10) in the utterance “Europe do not have money”. Besides, the comment in fragment (10) contains the tactic of *requesting information*, which also belongs to the strategy of *informing* (“Is it clear? Or shall I explain it to that rotten thing you call brain and soul?”). These comments are also very interesting examples of implementing the CONFRONTATION strategy, both with APPROACHING and DISTANCING. In example (9) implementing the CONFRONTATIVE DISTANCING can be concluded from the sceptic intonation of the whole message, while fragment (10) contains not only CONFRONTATIVE DISTANCING, observed in blaming the EU Commission President for taking money from the working population of EU, who pays taxes, to sponsor the war, as well as appealing to her religious values (“You will meet the Judge. <...> Check your birth date” where the word “Judge” means “God”), but also APPROACHING (primarily manifested in disrespect, that the commentator shows towards the politician addressing to her only by her first name in the comment “No, Ursula”).

Conclusions. The results of the conducted research allow us to conclude, that its hypothesis was approved: the global strategies implemented in political statements posted on social media have the capability of evoking CONFRONTATION in feedback to them, and, given that local strategies are one of their realisation instruments in the context of political statements, the taxonomy of the strategies, initially developed by E. Jones and T. S. Pittman to be applied for self-presentation, have perspectives to be used for strategic analysis of political discourse, which primarily aims at influencing the target audience. However, the analysed political statements did not show any potential of realising the local strategies of SELF-PROMOTION, which despite its similarity with that of INGRATIATION has more perspectives to be realised in the discourse of political debates; the strategies of INTIMIDATION and SUPPLICATION were detected occasionally. Regarding the taxonomy of speech strategies used to characterise

the comments to political statements *metaspeech* strategy was not detected to be implemented, which can be explained with its aims not corresponding the aims of analysed type of communication. It is also quite reasonable to conclude, that the range of global strategies implemented in political statements is rather wide, while All of the provided responses to the given fragments of political statements manifest attempts to resist being emotionally persuaded and/or manipulated via the CONFRONTATION strategy involvement, the presupposition of which can be formulated as follows: “I am not one to be fooled”. The practical significance of the present research lies, in particular, in its wide perspectives for further studies in the field of pragmatic linguistics and social linguistics, as well as shows a range of interdisciplinary connections with political science, psychology and sociology.

References:

1. Austin, J. L. (1962). *How to do things with words*. Harvard University Press.
2. Aristotle. (1991). *On rhetoric: A theory of civic discourse* (G. A. Kennedy, Trans.). Oxford University Press. (Original work published c. 350 BCE)
3. Aristotle. (1998). *Politics* (C. D. C. Reeve, Trans.). Hackett Publishing Company.
4. Barberá, P. (2020). Social media, echo chambers, and political polarization. In N. Persily & J. A. Tucker (Eds.), *Social media and democracy* (pp. 34–55). Cambridge University Press.
5. Benamara F., D., Inkpen, M., & Taboada, M. (2018). Introduction to the special issue on language in social media: Exploiting discourse and other contextual information. *Computational Linguistics*, 44(4), 663–681. https://doi.org/10.1162/coli_a_00333
6. Brüggemann, M., & Meyer, H. (2023). When debates break apart: Discursive polarization as a multi-dimensional divergence emerging in and through communication. *Communication Theory*, 33(2-3), 132–142. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ct/qtad012>
7. Chernyavskaya, V. E. (2006). *Diskurs vlasti i vlast' diskursa: Problemy rechevogo vozdeystviya* [Discourse of power and the power of discourse: Problems of speech influence]. Flinta-Nauka.
8. Chouliaraki, L. (2000). Political discourse in the news: Democratizing responsibility or aestheticizing politics? *Discourse & Society*, 11(3), 293–314.
9. Condor, S., Tileagă, C., & Billig, M. (2013). Political rhetoric. In L. Huddy, D. O. Sears, & J. S. Levy (Eds.), *The Oxford handbook of political psychology* (2nd ed., pp. 262–297). Oxford University Press.
10. Corbett, E. P. J. (1990). *Classical rhetoric for the modern student*. Oxford University Press.
11. Dijk, T. A. van. (1997). What is political discourse analysis. *Belgian Journal of Linguistics*, 11(1), 11–52.
12. Dijk, T. A. van. (2008). *Discourse and context: A sociocognitive approach*. Cambridge University Press.
13. Dijk, T. A. van. (2011). Principles of critical discourse analysis. In M. Wetherell, S. Taylor, & S. J. Yates (Eds.), *Discourse theory and practice: A reader* (pp. 300–317). Sage Publications.

14. Dijk, T. A. van. (Ed.). (1997). *Discourse as social interaction*. Sage Publications.
15. Encyclopedia Britannica. (n.d.). Rhetoric. Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/topic/rhetoric> (Access date: 29.06.2024)
16. Encyclopedia Britannica. (n.d.). Propaganda. Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/topic/propaganda>. (Access date: 05.01.2024)
17. Eyman, D. (2015). *Digital rhetoric: Theory, method, practice*. University of Michigan Press.
18. Ferrara, E. (2020). Misinformation, manipulation, and abuse on social media in the era of COVID-19. *Journal of Computational Social Science*.
19. Fetzer, A., & Lauerbach, G. (2007). *Political discourse in the media: Cross-cultural perspectives*. J. Benjamins Publishing Company.
20. Frolova, I. Ye. (2015). *Rehuliatyvnyi potensial stratehiyi konfrontatsiyi v anhlomovnomu dyskursi* [Regulatory potential of the strategy of confrontation in English discourse] (Doctoral dissertation). Kharkiv National University named after V. N. Karazin, Kharkiv, Ukraine.
21. Girth, H. (2002). *Sprache und Sprachverwendung in der Politik* [Language and language use in politics]. Westdeutscher Verlag.
22. Habermas, J. (1984–1987). *The theory of communicative action* (T. McCarthy, Trans.). Beacon Press. (Original work published 1981)
23. Habermas, J. (1991). *The structural transformation of the public sphere: An inquiry into a category of bourgeois society*. MIT Press. (Original work published 1962)
24. Habermas, J. (1996). *Between facts and norms: Contributions to a discourse theory of law and democracy*. MIT Press.
25. Hall, S. (1973). *Encoding and decoding in the television discourse*. University of Birmingham.
26. Herbig, A. F. (1992). "Sie argumentieren doch scheinlich!" Sprach- und sprechwissenschaftliche Aspekte einer Stilistik des Argumentierens ["You argue speciously!" Linguistic and rhetorical aspects of a stylistics of arguing]. Peter Lang.
27. Howell, B. (2020). Social media, censorship, and coddling internet users. *American Enterprise Institute - AEI*.
28. Huddy, L., Sears, D. O., Levy, J. S., & Jerit, J. (Eds.). (2023). *The Oxford handbook of political psychology* (3rd ed.). Oxford University Press. (Original work published 2003)
29. Ilchenko, M. L. (2014). *Henderna spetsyfika stratehii komunikativnoho dominuvannia v amerykans'kykh peredvybornykh teledebatakh* [Gender-specific strategies of communicative dominance in American pre-election TV debates] (PhD dissertation). Kharkiv.
30. Jones, E., & Pittman, T. S. (1982). Toward a general theory of strategic self-presentation. In *Psychological perspectives on the self* (Vol. 1, pp. 231–262). Lawrence Erlbaum.
31. Kabiri, M. (2018). *Self-presentation as a strategy of English discourse* (Doctoral dissertation). V. N. Karazin National University of Kharkiv.
32. Khodjayorov, M. B. (2022). Media linguistics and its role in the language of modern mass media. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology*, 10(IV).
33. Kubryakova, E. S., Demyankov, V. Z., Pankrat, Y. G., & Luzina, L. G. (Comps.). (1996). *Kratkii slovar' kognitivnykh terminov* [A concise dictionary of cognitive terms]. Moscow State University.
34. Language, discourse and social media. (n.d.). <https://www.kcl.ac.uk/abroad/module-options/language-discourse-and-social-media>. (Access date: 10.01.2024)
35. Losh, E. (2009). *Virtualpolitik: An electronic history of government media-making in a time of war, scandal, disaster, miscommunication, and mistakes*. MIT Press.
36. MacDonald, M. J. (2017). Introduction. In M. J. MacDonald (Ed.), *The Oxford handbook of rhetorical studies*. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780199731596.013.061>. (Access date: 05 Feb. 2024).
37. Malenkyi, B. I. (2018). *Argumentatyvni stratehii v nimets'komu ekonomichnomu dyskursi* (PhD dissertation). Kyiv.
38. Malishenko, A. O. (2010). *Henderni osoblyvosti anhlomovnoho reklamnoho dyskursu* (PhD dissertation). Kharkiv.
39. Mammadov, A., & Lewandowska-Tomaszczyk, B. (2022). *Analysing media discourse: Traditional and new*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
40. Martynyuk, A. P. (2015). Argumentatsiia ta sugestiiia yak instrumental'ni stratehii dyskursu. *Movni i kontseptual'ni kartyny svitu*, 55, 238–244.
41. Maslow, A. (1943). Theory of human motivation. *Psychological Review*, 50, 370–396.
42. Owen, D. The new media's role in politics. In *The age of perplexity: Rethinking the world we knew*. <https://www.bbvaopenmind.com/en/articles/the-new-media-s-role-in-politics/>
43. Oxford Internet Institute. (2021). Social media manipulation by political actors an industrial scale problem - Oxford report. *University of Oxford*.
44. Psikhologicheskii slovar' [Psychological dictionary]. (n.d.). <http://psychology.net.ru/dictionaries/psy/html?word>. (Access date: 31.07.2024)
45. Searle, J. R. (1969). *Speech acts: An essay in the philosophy of language*. Cambridge University Press.
46. Sergeev, V. M. (1987). Kognitivnye metody v sotsial'nykh issledovaniyakh. In *Yazyk i modelirovanie sotsial'nogo vzaimodeystviya* (pp. 3–20). Progress.
47. Siegel, D. A. (2013). Social networks and the mass media. *American Political Science Review*, 107(4), 786–805. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003055413000452>
48. Social media censorship and the law. (n.d.). <https://www.findlaw.com/civilrights/enforcing-your-civil-rights/social-media-censorship-and-the-law.html>. (Access date: 05.12.2023)
49. Stephen, K. (2021). The social responsibility of social media platforms. *The Regulatory Review*.

50. Stieglitz, S., & Dang-Xuan, L. (2013). Social media and political communication: A social media analytics framework. *Social Network Analysis and Mining*, 3(3), 1277–1291.
51. Sugestiya [Suggestion]. (n.d.). <https://psihomed.com/sugestiya>. (Access date: 29.07.2024)
52. Sun, Y., Wang, G., & Feng, H. (2021). Linguistic studies on social media: A bibliometric analysis. *SAGE Open*, 11(3).
53. Talbot, M. (2007). *Media discourse*. Edinburgh University Press.
54. Theil, S. (2022). Private censorship and structural dominance: Why social media platforms should have obligations to their users under freedom of expression. *The Cambridge Law Journal*, 81(3), 645–672. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0008197322000484>
55. Threats to freedom of press: Violence, disinformation & censorship. (n.d.). <https://www.unesco.org/en/threats-freedom-press-violence-disinformation-censorship>. (Access date: 12.12.2023)
56. Verba, S., Schlozman, K. L., Brady, H., & Nie, N. H. (1993). Citizen activity: Who participates, what do they say. *American Political Science Review*, 87(2), 303–318.
57. Wafiq, N. F. (2023). The power of social media: Shaping political discourse in the digital age. *Modern Diplomacy*. <https://moderndiplomacy.eu>. (Access date: 12.01.2024)
58. Wang, X., Sirianni, A. D., Tang, S., Zheng, Z., & Fu, F. (2020). Public discourse and social network echo chambers driven by socio-cognitive biases. *Physical Review X*, 10(4), 041042.
59. Warnick, B. (2007). *Rhetoric online: Persuasion and politics on the World Wide Web*. Peter Lang.
60. Wodak, R. (2003). Critical discourse analysis. In G. Weiss, & R. Wodak (Eds.), *Critical discourse analysis: Theory and interdisciplinarity* (pp. 1–34). Palgrave MacMillan.
61. Wodak, R. (2009). *The discourse of politics in action: Politics as usual*. Palgrave MacMillan.
62. Wodak, R. (2021). *The politics of fear: Fear as a driver of social and political change*. SAGE Publications.
63. Wratil, C., Wäckerle, J., & Proksch, S.-O. (2023). Government rhetoric and the representation of public opinion in international negotiations. *American Political Science Review*, 117(3), 1105–1122. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0003055422001198>
- Illustrative Material Sources**
64. @Alice_Weidel. (2024, August 16). [Tweet]. Retrieved from https://x.com/Alice_Weidel/status/1824355417385750910
65. @BoccardoReal. (2024, September 20). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/BoccardoReal/status/1837176325712531919>
66. @Bundeskanzler. (2024, September 6). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/Bundeskanzler/status/1832053269755031790>
67. @CharlesMichel. (2024, July 18). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/CharlesMichel/status/1813984412956021119>
68. @earthsoulrocknr. (2024, September 7). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/earthsoulrocknr/status/1832190813243166814>
69. @EP_President. (2024, September 19). [Tweet]. Retrieved from https://x.com/EP_President/status/1836717099340677489
70. @GuntherEagleman. (2024, July 12). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/GuntherEagleman/status/1811819423755567596>
71. @jensstoltenberg. (2024, September 6). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/jensstoltenberg/status/1831997368696230262>
72. @JoeBiden. (2024, July 13). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/JoeBiden/status/1811908837219192905>
73. @katcan426. (2024, June 3). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/katcan426/status/1797461017745842611>
74. @MarioFratto. (2024, July 13). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/MarioFratto/status/1811909193835905167>
75. @Panchenko_X. (2024, September 20). [Tweet]. Retrieved from https://x.com/Panchenko_X/status/1837105214597353846
76. @potus. (2024, July 12). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/potus/status/1811819068741013818?s=12>
77. @realTobiasR. (2024, September 7). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/realTobiasR/status/1832325598066180335>
78. @schoercher. (2024, August 16). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/schoercher/status/1824427731683012691>
79. @TheDagda_. (2024, September 19). [Tweet]. Retrieved from https://x.com/TheDagda_/status/1836740337588441200
80. @twist1961. (2024, July 19). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/twist1961/status/1814356221790482454>
81. @vonderleyen. (2024, September 20). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/vonderleyen/status/1837075615989780683>
82. @vonderleyen. (2024, September 20). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/vonderleyen/status/1837157613185679837>
83. @ZelenskyyUa. (2024, June 2). [Tweet]. Retrieved from <https://x.com/ZelenskyyUa/status/1797251142105129218>